
Influence of Human Resource Planning on Employee's Performance in National Insurance Corporation of Nigeria

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Abstract

The researchers empirically examined the influence of human resource planning on employees' performance at the NICON insurance company. It applied a descriptive survey research design, while primary sources of data were mainly used. The target population of the study is limited to 4 board members, 12 management team members and the entire staff and policyholders of Nicon Insurance Company within FCT, Abuja. A sample size of 200 respondents was determined using the Taro Yamane formula. A multiple regression analysis was employed. The researchers concluded that human resource planning influences employees performance at the National Insurance Corporation of Nigeria. The researchers among others recommended that the management of the NICON insurance company and the government of the day should endeavour to carry out a proper workforce forecasting to determine the right human capital and time necessary to get the right manpower into the organisation to thrive towards achieving efficiency.

Keywords: Human Capital Investment, Human Resource Planning, Efficiency, Manpower Forecasting, Staffing

Introduction

The universe is an organised world and the almighty, creator of the universe, made all things in a sequence of proper planning and coordination, such that things keep falling in their proper places at the set times and seasons. Therefore, planning is as old as man; it is the first and most important aspect of management. Failure to plan is planning to fail. A plan is a road map or guide towards action that helps the organisation achieve its objectives. This study considers planning as an aspect of human resource management, a process of setting or drawing out organisational goals and streamlining them into achievable objectives, determining resources and activities that are necessary to achieve the set target with evaluation and control measures (Iwuozor & Onibon, 2022). It is important to keep up with the current global trends, which have dehumanised human efforts and impeded human ability to utilise capabilities, skills and competencies to meet the global demand of customers. According to Tonderai (2013), the matching process to bring about equilibrium in demand and supply of workforce due to a shortage in manpower and the issue of overstaffing needs to be solved.

On the other hand, performance is the process or act of accomplishing a task or action; employees' performance is appraised against preset standards. Many measures of performance may be more relevant to some sectors than others. According to Abdel-

Maksoud, Asada & Nakagawa (2008), the major performance measurement is quantity, which is basically the number of units produced, processed, or sold against the set standard. It is also measured with productivity. According to Bature (2022), productivity depends on the quality of human resources as well as their effective use, adding that it implies output per man hour and quality, which can be measured as a percentage of work output that must be redone or rejected, is one such indicator. In a sales environment, the percentage of inquiries converted to sales is an indicator of salesmanship among others and the measurement yardstick varies from industry to industry.

According to Anyanwu (1993), the Nigerian insurance company can be traced to the introduction of the royal exchange assurance in 1921 in Lagos Colony. The number kept increasing through the amalgamation of foreign and indigenous insurance companies, such that by 1960, the number rose to 25, for a total of 107 in 1993. The NICON Insurance PLC was initially established by the federal government of Nigeria, under No. 22 of 1769 (as amended by Cap. 263 of 1990) as fully owned by the federal government for the ownership and domination of their foreign counterparts and other insurance companies in the Nigerian market were threatened in July 1969 with the promulgation of Decree 22. This Decree outlined the functions and activities of NICON as well as a wide range of insurance policies covered by the company, ranging from life assurance to property insurance: it covers motor insurance, fire insurance, goods in transit, professional indemnity, traveller's insurance, performance bonds and life assurance, among others (Ekezie, 2002). The leadership position of the company in the Nigerian insurance industry was not only recognised, but also justifiably respected because it is consulted by the government, state and federal governments on insurance matters and the company has used its position of strength to assist in settling up new state-owned insurance companies and provide remedies for ailing ones in many cases.

The company has also been playing a leadership role in the development of manpower for the Nigerian insurance industry (Akpan, 1999). However, a lot had changed since ownership of the company was shifted to private ownership in 2006. Since then, the company has taken on a different shape and dimension, especially in the area of human resource planning. This study is, therefore, set out to look into the resource planning activities of the company and employees performance.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the vital roles played by human resource planning in business organisations, the acute shortage of qualified manpower has caused serious problems facing NICON Insurance Company. A preliminary investigation reveals that staff stay long in the organisation, not because of the job enrichment, welfare or compensation packages they receive, but because they do not have enough promising alternatives out there. Some of the staff always complain of delays in salaries and many times, the backlog of salaries is partly paid and others forfeited. However, it is not known if these phenomena are directly linked to the dwindling staff morale of the employees, the delivery of quality service and modality and why a lot of staff absent themselves from work. On the other hand, the limited staff in the organisation appears to be overloaded owing to the general perception

that overstaffing is expensive and this may be responsible for the level of fatigue, burnout and professional dissatisfaction, which may negatively impede the level of expected returns on investment in human resource capital and other stakeholders' benefits. Some stakeholder groups have also complained that some of the funds for the coordination of the workforce are always converted to private pockets by the top management. In view of the above, the researchers have taken up the issue of human resources planning and employees performance in business organisations with specific reference to NICON Insurance in Abuja.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Assess the effect of manpower forecasting and employees' efficiency among staff of NICON insurance company.
2. Determine the relationship between staffing and return of human capital investment in NICON insurance company.

Research Hypotheses

The hypotheses below were tested:

Ho₁: Manpower forecasting has no significant effect on employees' efficiency among staff of NICON insurance company.

Ho₂: Staffing has no significant effect on return of human capital investment in NICON insurance company.

Literature Review

Planning is very pivotal to organisational success when it comes to human resources. Human resource planning is also referred to as workforce planning or personnel planning. According to Nwichi & Chukwuka (2017), the movement of people into and out of the organisation is the focus of human resources planning, which entails obtaining and applying pertinent data to support decisions on human resource management and resource allocation for the organisation's labour-intensive operations.

Bature (2013) adds that it involves a rational approach to the effective recruitment, retention and deployment of people within the organisation, as well as the necessary conditions for the dismissal of workers. To achieve the efficiency of human resources in terms of return on human resource investment, human resource planning has to be strategic. Strategic workforce planning ensures that qualified employees are available when the organisation needs them.

Performance is the way of execution of an action, process or operation. However, the focus of the study is human resources performance, which is achieved through return on human resource investment in training new and current employees. To ensure that there is an adequate return on human resource investment, the organisation has to establish key performance indicators.

Employee performance indicators serve as a benchmark for measuring the progress of employees towards a set of broader-based goals or objectives (Samuel, 2018).

However, most organisations are faced with the challenges of developing good performance when it comes to human resources planning. Samuel (2018) suggests that quality key performance indicators for tracking human resource planning effectiveness should include a measurable indicator that is based on competence. This explains the efficiency of employees and quantifiable indicators, which implies quality service delivery; competency-based indicators; linked to proficiency indicators; and mapped to organisational success and employee goals indicators.

Okafor, Okonkwo & Essell (2022) looked at how organisational performance in the south-east Nigerian brewery sector was affected by manpower planning. Regression analysis, summary and descriptive statistics and a descriptive survey design were the primary analytical methods employed in this study. The coefficient of determination indicated that the regressors could account for 52.9% of the variation in the dependent variable.

Igbokwe, Osakede & Anazodo (2017) found that the curriculum for workforce planning and development had a favourable impact on the performance of the Lagos State Civil Service.

Theoretical Framework

Douglas McGregor's

According to theory X, people are unreliable and should be motivated to do their work by using the stick sparingly, not the carrot. As a result, management based on this assumption is coercive and manipulative, according to McGregor (1960), as cited in Tihanyi (2000).

The assumption of theory Y is that people have a capacity to be highly imaginative and creative; physical and mental work is as natural as play or rest; people will exercise self-direction and self-control in meeting any objective to which they are committed. People are not by nature passive or resistant to organisational goals; workers are willing to accept and will even seek responsibility, according to McGregor (1960), as cited in Tihanyi (2000).

This study is underpinned by this theory because according to McGregor, Theory X and Y's views of workers are not opposite ends of the same continuum, but rather two different continua in themselves. In order to achieve the most efficient performance in an organisation, a combination of the views of both theories may be appropriate for formulating strategic human resource plans.

Method

Survey design was adopted in this study. The reason for using the survey approach is that it allows the collection of a significant amount of data in an economical and efficient manner (Mohammed, 2005). Population refers to all the inhabitants within the study boundary that fall within the subject of the research (Okeke, 1995). Therefore, the population of this study consists of the 4 Board of Directors, 12 management team members and the entire staff and policyholders of Nikon Insurance Company within FCT, Abuja.

The sampling technique adopted in this study is the purposive sampling technique. The researchers applied purposive sampling to conveniently consider 170 policyholders and 30 staff of Nikon Insurance Company within FCT, Abuja. This gives a total of 200 samples which is the sample size. The study used basically primary data. The primary source of data was a well-structured questionnaire that was administered to the respondents. A number of statistics, such as frequency counts and percentages, were put to use in the analysis of research questions, while research hypotheses were tested using the multiple regression tool of analysis, at which the 0.05 level was the significant level for testing the hypothesis and the analysis was carried out with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

In order to assess the influence of human resource planning on performance of small and medium enterprises, a multiple regression model was built:

$$P = \alpha + \beta_1MPF + \beta_2S + \epsilon \dots \dots \dots i$$

Where MPF = Manpower forecasting , S = Staffing ,E = efficiency & ROI= Return of Human capital investment, α = Intercept, $\beta_{1,2}$ = Independent variable, ϵ = Error term , P= Performance Which is the independent variable

Hypotheses testing and Regression Result

The hypothesis formulated in chapter one of this study was verified in order to find out the validity or otherwise of such a proposition. The research hypothesis was based on relevant statistics from the regression result, which is tested on the basis of quantitative statistical analysis in this study.

Table 1 Regression of the Influence of Human Resource Planning on the Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises

Model	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
(Constant)	2.282	.297		7.688	.000
1 Manpower forecasting	.399	.096	.284	4.148	.000
Staffing	.209	.195	.073	1.070	.286

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Source; SPSS Output, version 21

Table 2: Model Summary of the Influence of Human Resource Planning on the Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises

Model Summary ^b						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson	
1	.287 ^a	.082	.073	1.10917	2.081	

a. Predictors: (Constant), manpower planning, staffing

b. Dependent Variable: performance

Source; SPSS Output, version 21

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Manpower forecasting has no significant effect on employees' efficiency in NICON insurance company

Looking at the regression result as calculated in table 2, it is clear that the value of manpower planning is 399 and its probability is 0.000, which indicates that manpower planning is positively significant. Furthermore, since its probability (0.000) is less than the 0.05% level of significance, we reject the null hypothesis (H₀) and accept the alternative hypothesis (H₁), which says that manpower planning has a significant impact on the efficiency of employees in the NICON insurance company.

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Staffing has no significant effect on return of human capital investment in NICON insurance company.

Inferring from table 2 analysis, it was discovered that the government policy computed has a value of .209 against the probability of 0.286, revealing that staffing is not significant. Furthermore, since its probability (0.209) is less than the 0.05% level of significance, based on this analysis, we accept (H₀) and reject (H₁), which implies that staffing has no significant impact on the return of human capital investment in the NICON insurance company.

Discussion of the Findings

The study analysed the influence of human resource planning on employees' performance at the National Insurance Corporation of Nigeria. The findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between manpower forecasting and the efficiency of the performance of NICON Insurance Company, while staffing has no significant impact on the return on human capital investment in NICON Insurance Company. It was noted earlier in this work that inefficient manpower planning will give rise to poor performance for the organisation, as workforce forecasting is a crucial factor in attaining efficiency in NICON because failure to plan is planning to fail. Proper workforce planning gives rise to better human resource practices, which will increase the return on human capital investment and above all, the employees' performance, thus increasing the achievement of overall organisational objectives. These findings are in line with the work of Igbokwe, Osakede & Anazodo (2017) and Bello, Okafor & Onifade (2017) who found that human resource planning has a positive influence on achieving organisational objectives.

The findings showed that there is no significant relationship between staffing and the return on human capital investment in the NICON insurance company. Data analysed in light of this showed that to achieve a return on human capital investment, workforce forecasting is ranked higher in the NICON insurance company than staffing. This is because workforce forecasting is the first and most important aspect of human resource planning as a base for staffing functions, while a good staffing function involves the introduction of various activities such as recruitment, selection, and placement. The finding is in line with the findings of Dunmade, Kadiri, Aun, Bello &

Yahaya (2019) who pointed out that job security is the most applied HRM practice compared to staffing, which is based on proper workforce planning.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The researchers empirically examined the influence of human resources planning on employees' performance in the NICON insurance company. The findings showed that manpower forecasting has a significant effect on employee efficiency among staff of NICON Insurance Company and staffing has a significant effect on the return on human capital investment in NICON Insurance Company. In line with the findings of the study, it was concluded that human resource planning influences employee performance at the National Insurance Corporation of Nigeria. Thus, the following recommendations are hereby given:

1. The management of the NICON insurance company and the government of the day should endeavour to carry out proper workforce forecasting to determine the right human capital and timely necessary to get the right manpower into the organisation to thrive towards achieving the efficiency of the organisation.
2. Staffing goals should be properly defined and established based on proper forecasting and the staff should be well retained through the right welfare packages to ensure the return of human capital investment.

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